

Strategic Manufacturing for Sovereignty, Sustainability and Skills

Best practice category

Strengthening manufacturing capacities; New impetus for chip design; Funding and policy

Stakeholder group

Large enterprises

Value chain position

IDM (Integrated Device Manufacturer); Equipment; R&D

General Information

Infineon Technologies is a leading European semiconductor company, headquartered in **Neubiberg, Germany**. It operates as an **Integrated Device Manufacturer (IDM)**, covering the entire value chain: from chip design to large-scale production, up to commercialisation. With a global presence and approximately 58,000 employees, Infineon is one of the world's leading providers of solutions for **power electronics, automotive, Internet of Things (IoT), integrated security** and **artificial intelligence**.

The company is organised into four main divisions: **Automotive (ATV)**: technologies for electric mobility, autonomous driving and on-board electronics; **Green Industrial Power (GIP)**: solutions for green energy, industrial electrification and intelligent energy management; **Power & Sensor Systems (PSS)**: devices for efficient power control, intelligent sensors, connectivity and miniaturisation; **Connected Secure Systems (CSS)**: microcontrollers, security solutions, connectivity and systems for IoT applications. Infineon is recognised for its leadership in advanced materials such as **silicon carbide (SiC)** and **gallium nitride (GaN)**, critical for high-efficiency next-generation electronic devices.

Activities and best practices

- By managing all development phases internally, Infineon reduces dependence on **external suppliers**, accelerates time to market and guarantees operational continuity. This approach is crucial for strengthening the EU's technological sovereignty in the context of fragile global supply chains.
- Infineon has undertaken important infrastructure investments to strengthen its production capacity on European soil, in particular in the power electronics sector. A case in point is the construction of the new **Smart Power Fab in Dresden**, one of the most advanced and large-scale semiconductor manufacturing plants currently under construction in Europe. This project represents a concrete commitment to support European industrial resilience, helping to ensure the secure supply of critical components for strategic sectors such as automotive, aerospace, energy and defence. The **Smart Power Fab** was also born as a response to two central global challenges: **digitalisation** and **decarbonisation**. Both will require a growing demand for semiconductors, and through the innovative solutions developed and produced in Dresden, Infineon intends to actively support the transition towards a digital and climate-neutral world.

- Infineon is leading the transition to a circular economy in the semiconductor industry through concrete initiatives involving both its operations and supplier network. Among these, the **reuse of wafer boxes** in the production sites of **Kulim, Villach** and **Dresden** stands out, the reintroduction of **discarded wafers** as wafer monitors thanks to an innovative **refurbishing process**, and the collaboration with **Applied Materials** for the recovery and repair of industrial components complexes.
- Infineon actively supports the development of specialist skills through integrated doctoral programs in collaboration with universities and centers of excellence, such as the Kompetenzzentrum Automobil- und Industrieelektronik (KAI) in Austria. Young researchers can work on innovative topics directly in the company, with three-year contracts, while carrying out a doctoral thesis in line with their studies.

Challenges addressed with this practice

In a global context marked by fragility of supply chains and geopolitical competition, the company actively contributes to the technological sovereignty of the EU, strengthening production capacity on European soil and reducing dependence on non-European suppliers. Initiatives in the circular economy address the urgent need to reduce the environmental impact of the sector, contributing to the transition to more sustainable industrial models through the reuse of materials, chemical recycling and the reduction of Scope 3 emissions. At the same time, Infineon responds to the lack of highly specialised skills in the deep tech sector, promoting advanced training courses through doctoral programs integrated with universities and research centres. Finally, with its solutions in power electronics, electric mobility, IoT and AI, it supports the great twin transitions of decarbonisation and digitalisation, key pillars of the European agenda for sustainable innovation.